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Impact Factor: 3.43

Cite this paper as : Inderpreet Singh (2017), "CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS ELECTRIC FANS", International Journal of Marketing & Financial Management, ISSN: 2348 –3954 (online) ISSN: 2349 –2546 (print), Volume 5,(Issue 4, Apr-2017), pp 42-53,

CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR TOWARDS ELECTRIC FANS

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ABSTRACT

The study of consumer behaviour develops great interest for consumers, students, scientists, and marketers. As consumers, we need insights into our own consumption related decisions: what we buy, why we buy, and how we buy. The aim of the study is to cover entire research about consumer behaviour towards electric fans and different factors affecting their buying decision. A sample of 200 consumers of electric fans is taken. Questionnaire has been analysed with the help of pie diagram & bar chart and different interpretations have been made to study the impact of consumer behaviour towards electric fans. This study concluded that the brand whose after Sales Service is more satisfactory get the positive response from customers. Price is the most important attribute which attracts consumer towards particular brand.

Key words: Electric Fan, Consumer behaviour, buying decision

INTRODUCTION

The term consumer behaviour is defined as the behaviour that consumer display in searching for, purchasing, using, evaluating and disposing of product, services and ideas that they expect will satisfy their needs. The study of consumer behaviour is the study of how individual make decisions to spend their available resources (money, time, and effort) on consumption-related items. It includes the study of what they buy, why they buy it, how they buy it, when they buy it, where they buy it, and how often they buy it. Thus the study of an consumer behaviour in the area of electric fans might include a study of why he uses a particular brand (price-quality), which brand of electric fans he buys (e.g. Havells, cromption etc), how he buys it (for cash, credit or by coupon), where he buys it (from ordinary shop, company's outlet),and how often he buys it (approximately every six months, an year).

Although consumer behaviour focus on how and why consumers make decisions to buy goods and services but now consumer behaviour research today goes for beyond these facets of consumer behaviour. Research also considers the uses consumers make of the goods they buy and their evaluation of these goods after use. In addition to studying consumer's use and post purchase evaluation of the product they buy, consumer researchers are also interested in how individuals dispose of their once-new purchases. For example, after using a product for many months, do consumer's, throw it or give it away, sell it, rent it, or lend it out? The answer to this question is important to marketers because they must match their production to the frequency with which consumers buy replacements. Research into current disposal practices enables marketers to develop and promote environmentally sound and economically efficient consumer product. Consumer behaviour is the process whereby, individuals decide whether, what, when, where, how, and from whom to purchase goods and services.

According to Peter F. Drucker, "it is the consumer who determines what a business is, for it is the customer and he alone who through being willing to pay for goods and services converts economic resources into wealth, things Into goods. What a business thinks it produce is not of first importance especially not to the future of the business and to it's e.g., what considers "value" is decisive. It determines what a business is, what it produces and whether it will prosper." Consumer behaviour consists of the mental and physical activities for acquiring the

products (which are themselves bundles of physical and psychological satisfactions) and obtain satisfaction from them. Another feature of consumer behaviour is that It includes both observable physical and mental activities. Physical activities can be walking through the stores and examining the merchandise while mental activities can be forming attitudes, perceiving advertising materials and learning to prefer particular brands. Attitudes and preferences can be determined by studying shopping, purchasing, motivation, perception, attitude change, and personality of the buyers.

The study of consumer behaviour holds great interest for us as consumers, as students and scientists, and as marketers. As consumers, we need Insights into our own consumption related decisions: what we buy, why we buy, and how we buy. The study of consumer behaviour makes us aware of the subtle Influences that pursued us to make the product or service choices we do. As a student of human behaviour, it is important for us to understand the internal and external influences that Impel individuals to act In certain consumption-related ways. Consumer behaviour is simply a sub set of the larger field of human behaviour. As scientist, we are interested in understanding every aspect of human behaviour. As marketers, It is important for us to recognize why and how individuals make their consumption decisions so that we can make better strategic marketing decisions. Without doubt, marketers who understand consumer behaviour have great competitive advantages in the market place.

What is Consumer Behaviour?

Consumer Behaviour is a rapidly growing discipline of study. It means more than just how a person buys products. It is a complex and multidimensional process and reflects the totality of consumer's decisions with respect to acquisition, consumption and disposal activities. We, as consumers, exhibit very significant differences in our buying behaviour and play an Important role In local, national or International economy conditions. One of the very few aspects common to all of us Is that we are all consumers and the reason for a business firm to come into being is the presence of consumers who have unfulfilled, or partially fulfilled needs and wants. No matter who we are - urban or rural, male or female, young or old, rich or poor, educated or uneducated, believer or non-believer, or whatever - we are all consumers. We consume or use on a regular basis food, shelter, clothing, education, entertainment, brooms, toothbrushes, vehicles, domestic help, healthcare and other services, necessities, comforts, luxuries and even ideas etc. Organisations realise that their marketing effectiveness in satisfying consumer needs and wants at a profit depends on a deeper understanding of consumer behaviour. Our consumption related behaviour influences the development of technology and introduction of new and improved products and services. Some of the important issues that marketing executives face include:

- What do consumers think about our products and those of our competitors?
- What do they think of possible improvements in our products?
- What are their attitudes toward our products and our promotional, efforts?
- What they feel are their roles in the family and society?
- What are their hopes and dreams for themselves and their families?

To succeed in a dynamic marketing environment, marketers have an urgent need to learn and anticipate whatever they can about consumers. The better they know and understand consumers, the more advantageous it would prove in accomplishing their organizational objectives. Marketers want to know what consumers think, what they want, how they work, how they entertain themselves, how they play etc. They also need to comprehend personal and group influences which have a significant impact on consumer decision-making process.

CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR ABOUT ELECTRIC FANS

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LITERATURE REVIEW

Alba and Hutchinson, (2000) Consumer decision making process is usually guided by already formed preferences for a particular alternative. This means that consumers are likely to make the choice between alternatives based on limited information search activity and without detailed evaluation of the other alternatives. **Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry (1988)** developed a survey instrument SERVQUAL to measure the customer's perception of service quality against parameters such as Tangibles, Reliability, Assurance, Empathy and Responsiveness. However, Cronin. Because theoretical problems and ambiguities must be resolved before operational issues can be addressed effectively, his response focuses on the Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1994) comments concerning (1) the theoretical problems associated with the SERVQUAL P - E model and (2) the Teas (1993) evaluated performance (EP) and normed quality (NQ) models. In addition, he assesses the theoretical merit of the Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1994) SERVQUAL "mixed-model." His primary conclusions are that the conclusions reached by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1994) with

respect to the Teas (1993) EP and NQ models are incorrect and that the proposed SERVQUAL mixed-model is merely a restricted version of (i. e., a re-expression that is less general than) the Teas (1993) NQ model. It is no secret that businesses main goal is to sale and sale is provided for other party consumers therefore for commercial activities analysing consumer behaviour is crucial (**Deaton and Muellbauer, 1980, Solomon, 2006, Wright and et al., 2008**) and since there is face to face interaction it becomes more important to understand key features of consumer behaviour. **Nazir, et al., 2012** indicates the importance of the relationship between the marketing strategy and the behaviour of consumer. He interest rates that the strategy is about increasing the probability and frequency of buyer behaviour and requirements for succeeding in doing this to know the customer and understand consumers needs and wants. **Hong Qin and Victor R Prybutok (2008)** studied the fast food restaurants and determined that service quality has an overwhelmingly direct effect on behavioral intentions but not on satisfaction. This suggests the existence of some other factors such as speed of service, proximity of the location contributing to the customer satisfaction. **Debasish and Dey (2015)** found the perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, relative advantages, perceived risks and personal innovativeness were the factors affecting the behavioural intentions of mobile users to adopt mobile services in Odisha. Meanwhile, an expected, the perceived risk was the only factor found to have negative relationship with the adoption of mobile banking in this study which the only factors are positively correlated.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

Significance of the Electric fans is very important to everyone, not even in India but it is a worldwide phenomenon. This study has been conducted to check consumer preferences and towards fans and to find out the best quality fan in Delhi region. Several studies have been conducted on the use of electric fans among people in different countries across the world such as Japan, Norway, Finland, USA, and Britain. This study adds to the growing body of research by providing empirical information about the study which helps companies to make product according to customer needs and wants and provide best quality services to retailers in India. Several studies have been suggested about the fans, give little hints about the fans industry. However, in India the studies have only looked at few of these issues . This study provides information about the variety of electric fans uses by people in Delhi region (India)

From the theoretical point of view, this study contributes to the academic literature by providing evidence for the theories used in this study. By applying the uses and gratifications perspective, this study shows that what type of changes consumer and wants, suggestion of consumers in relation to price, demand, choice, their brand loyalty. Through the application of Field survey conducted, this study provides evidence that consumer wants to make changes in price of some fans products, and want improved after sales services.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study is based on the following objectives:

1. To study the consumer behaviour about electric fans.
2. To study the attributes that attracts consumers to purchase Electric.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Scope of the study:

The scope of the study is to get the firsthand knowledge about the buying behaviour of consumers and towards different brands of Electric fans in Delhi region. The scope is restricted to study the factors affecting the preference of consumers and while choosing Electric fans. This is done to avoid perceptual bias and for providing objectivity to the study.

Data type:

Primary Data

Primary data is that data which is collected for the first time. For the purpose of collection of primary data, a well-structured questionnaire was framed which was filled by the respondents.

Secondary Data

Secondary data is the data which is already collected by someone. Secondary data was collected so as to have accurate results .Required data was collected from various books, magazines, journals and internet.

Size:

Active consumers of Electric Product: 200

Analytical tool:

Charts, pie charts. Diagrams, Ranks, Weighted Rank and Percentage.

Brand Name	Frequency of Viewers	Percentage
Crompton	90	17.57
Havells	118	23.04
Usha	106	20.70
Orient	95	18.94
Bajaj	93	18.16
Others	10	1.95
Total		100

ANALYTICAL OVERVIEW

1. Brand names of electric fans consumers are aware of

Table 1.1 : Awareness of Brand Names

Source: Primary Data

Figure 1

Figure 2

Interpretation: A survey of 200 consumers from Delhi was undertaken, where they asked to tick the Brand name of Electric Fans they know. According to analysis, it is clear that majority of consumers know about **Havells (118 Consumers)** followed by **Usha (106 Consumers)**. This indicates that Havells is a renowned name in Delhi Region.

2. Source from where customers get information about fans.

Table No. 1.2: Different Media Approach

Information Source	Frequency of Viewers	Percentage
Advertising	89	25.50
Promotions	101	28.93
Retail Outlets	97	27.79
Family/ Friends	53	15.18
Word of mouth	9	2.57
Others	0	0
Total		100

Source: Primary Data

Figure 3

Figure 4

Interpretation: The data mentioned in Table. 1.2 represents the information source. How does consumer knows about a particular Brand. The above analysis shows that majority of the consumers knows about a Brand through the **Promotional Activities** undertaken by the particular Brand followed by **Retail Outlets**, where consumers personally visits and collect information about fans before purchasing them.

3. Most preferred brand of electric fans.

Table 1.3: Ranks are given by consumers.

Rank =>	1	2	3	4	5	6	Total	Average
Brand Name								
Crompton	46	44	41	42	24	1	198	33
Havells	53	57	51	26	12	0	199	33.17
Usha	47	52	30	36	27	5	197	32.83
Orient	28	27	45	53	46	1	200	33.33
Bajaj	23	20	30	39	90	0	202	33.37
Others	3	0	3	4	1	187	198	33
Total	200	200	200	200	200	194	1194	

Source: Primary Data

Table 1.4: Weights are given to different Brands

Ranks	Weights	Crompton	Havells	Usha	Orient	Bajaj	Others
1	20	920	1060	940	560	460	60
2	18	792	1026	936	486	360	0
3	16	752	816	480	720	480	48
4	14	588	364	504	742	546	56
5	12	288	144	324	552	1080	12
6	10	10	0	50	10	0	1870

Source: Primary Data

Table 1.5: Ranking of Brands according to their total weights

Weighted Rank	Brands
1	Havells
2	Usha
3	Crompton
4	Orient
5	Bajaj
6	Others

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: In the analysis, consumer is asked to rank the most preferred brand according to themselves. An analysis is done on 200 consumers in which they rank the brand according to their preference.

To make the analysis valuable, weights are given to each rank. Rank 1 is very important, so highest rank is given to it, followed by Rank 2 and Rank 3 and so on.

According to weighted rank, it is clear that majority of consumers has given the Rank1 to Havells. It means that majority of the consumers preferred Havells over other Brands followed by Usha as they given Rank 2 to Usha and then Rank 3 to Crompton.

4. Brand which the consumers are currently using.

Table 1.6 : Users of different brands

Brand Name	Frequency of Viewers	Percentage
Crompton	56	21.70
Havells	72	27.90
Usha	56	21.70
Orient	40	15.50
Bajaj	33	12.79
Others	1	0.38
Total		100

Source: Primary Data

Figure - 5

Figure - 6

Interpretation: The information in Table 1.6 shows that from among different Brands which Brand majority of the consumers are using. It shows their preference towards the particular brand. From the analysis, it is clear that majority of the consumers are using **Havells** followed by **Crompton** and **Usha**.

This comes out with the conclusion that in Delhi Region, Havells is the most preferred brand by consumers as it get the highest ratings than other Brands.

5. Time duration of consumers using a particular Brand.

Table 1.7: Time Duration Recorded

Time Period	Number of Viewers	Percentage
Less than 3 months	6	3
Less than 6 months	24	12
Less than 1 Year	44	22
More than 1 Year	126	63
Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Figure 7

Interpretation: Information in Table 1.7 shows that how long a consumer can stick to a particular Brand without switching to other Brand. Above analysis shows that consumer switching cost is high as they don't switch to other brand easily, if they are satisfied with the Brand they are using.

Around 63% of consumers have been using their Brand for more than 1 year. This is a very high percentage which clearly indicates that consumers don't switch to other Brand easily. After conversating with them, they clearly said that if they don't find any problem with the Brand they are using, they don't switch to other Brand unnecessarily.

6. Satisfaction of consumers with the brand they are using.

Table 1.8: Consumer Satisfaction Disclosure

Response	Number of Respondants	Percentage
Yes	198	99
No	2	1
Total	200	100

Source: Primary Data

Figure - 8

Interpretation: Information given in table 1.8 shows that, if the consumers are satisfied with the Brand, they are currently using or not.

It clearly concluded that **99%** of the consumers are satisfied with the Brand they are using. As they don't find any problems with the Brand they are using currently and they are fully satisfied with their After Sales Service and Performance.

1% consumers are not satisfied, as they mentioned that they are not satisfied with After Sales Service of the Brand they are using. If the problem arises with the Fan, they need to make several calls to Company's Service Center for technician services which irritates the consumer because of unsatisfactory response.

7. Attribute that attract consumers to purchase Electric fan. Ranking is given by consumers.

Table 1.9: Ranks are given to Attributes

Rank => Attributes	1	2	3	4	Total	Average
Price	64	73	49	10	196	49
Convenience	42	53	53	52	200	50
After Sales Service	30	49	59	56	194	48.5
Brand Name	61	22	34	80	196	49
Total	197	197	194	198	786	

Source: Primary Data

Table 1.10: Weights are assigned to different attributes

Ranks	Weights	Price	Convenience	After Sales Service	Brand Name
1	20	1280	840	600	1220
2	18	1314	954	882	396
3	16	784	848	944	544
4	14	140	728	784	1120

Source: Primary Data

Table 1.11: Weighted Rank is given

Weighted Rank	Attributes
1	Price
2	Convenience
3	After Sales Service
4	Brand Name

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation: From the analysis, consumer is asked about to Rank the attributes which attracts them to purchase a particular Brand. Different attributes have been given above ex- Price, Convenience, After Sales Service, Brand Name.

An analysis is done on 200 consumers, Different views has been taken from them and noted down. Weights have been assigned to them according to their preference.

According to weighted rank, it is clear that Price is the main attribute which people look before they purchase a particular brand followed by convenience and after sales service

CONCLUSION OF THE STUDY

The study concluded that most of the consumer is aware about the brands. They get information about fans through advertising, promotions, family and friends. The brand whose after Sales Service is satisfactory get the positive response from consumers. Majority of the customers are using the specific brand for a very long period of time which concluded that consumer does not switch easily from one brand to another. Price is the most important attribute which attracts consumer towards particular brand. The findings of the study will also help the researchers and academicians in understanding the consumer behaviour with the help of different factors influence the consumer buying decision.

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